

Genetic analysis of *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici* in Bhutan highlights the need for increased surveillance

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Wheat stem rust, caused by the fungus *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pgt*), has historically caused devastating yield losses in wheat-dependent regions of South Asia, but has been under control in recent decades largely due to the use of resistant cultivars. In this study, we set out to investigate *Pgt* occurrence within Bhutan, where we recorded a total of four *Pgt* samples recovered from the Haa district in 2025, confirming *Pgt* presence in the country. To compare these *Pgt* samples to global isolates of *Pgt*, each sample was genotyped using our Mobile And Real-time PLant disEase (MARPLE) diagnostics genotyping platform. Subsequent phylogenetic analysis indicted a close genetic relationship between all four Bhutanese *Pgt* samples and other *Pgt* strains previously identified within neighbouring Nepal. Furthermore, we identified several mutations in target genes (*Cyp51* and *SdhD*) for two major fungicides used to control wheat rust worldwide. This included mutations in *Cyp51* (S208T and V490L) that were ubiquitous in all 102 additional *Pgt* representative isolates analysed that represent the major *Pgt* race groups in the MARPLE diagnostics pipeline and are analogous to mutations previously reported to lower sensitivity to demethylation inhibitor (DMI) azole fungicides in *Zymoseptoria tritici*. This initial analysis indicates that *Pgt*, with genetic similarity to Clade IV, is present in Bhutan and that enhanced surveillance effects are needed to comprehensively define the *Pgt* population structure and further monitor for any potential changes in fungicide efficacy in the region.

Introduction

Since the beginning of the 21st century wheat production in Bhutan has been declining, with farmers opting for more lucrative, high-yielding crops, like rice (1,2). However, in more recent years wheat cultivation has reportedly experienced a steady increase, following various government-led programs to promote wheat production, especially for durum wheat (*Triticum durum*). This follows the establishment of a new evolving pasta industry reliant on *T. durum* and supported by government initiatives, such as the Agriculture Research and Development Centre (ARDC) Bajo and Farm Machinery Corporation Limited (FMCL). However, the risks posed by fluctuating temperatures, erratic rainfall patterns and rising biotic stressors, still largely undermine wheat cultivation and force farmers in Bhutan to seek production of alternative, high yielding and less vulnerable crops. Among biotic stressors, the stem rust pathogen *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pgt*) represents a particularly concerning threat. Unlike yellow rust, caused by the related pathogen *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pst*), which has historically been a persistent challenge to wheat farmers in Bhutan, *Pgt* has only recently been detected in Bhutan ([Global Rust Reference Center](#), 2024; (3)). Thus, making sightings of *Pgt* a significant concern given its potential for rapid spread and severe yield losses (4).

Pgt is heteroecious and reproduces asexually on wheat and sexually on *Berberis* spp., with the latter leading to emergence of abundant novel pathogen genotypes (5). Bhutan is recognized as a global hotspot for *Berberis* diversity, which has been linked to the greater diversity in the *Pst* population in the country, similar to other neighbouring Himalayan countries, such as Nepal and Pakistan (6). Here, we set out to conduct an initial assessment of *Pgt* occurrence in Bhutan. This included utilisation of our Mobile And Real-time PLant disEase (MARPLE) diagnostics platform that can be used for rapid strain-level diagnostics of *Pst* and *Pgt* strains and was recently deployed in the region (7,8). We confirmed that *Pgt* was present in 2025 in Bhutan and that *Pgt* strains present are genetically similar to *Pgt* strains previously identified within neighbouring countries in the region. We also identified mutations in target genes for two critical fungicides used for tackling wheat rusts worldwide, the azoles and succinate dehydrogenase inhibitors. However, we note that these mutations in *Cyp51* and *SdhD* were also present in *Pgt* isolates from several other countries that are included in the MARPLE diagnostic pipeline as representatives of the major *Pgt*

race groups. Overall, this analysis indicates that enhanced surveillance efforts are required to comprehensively define the *Pgt* population in Bhutan.

Materials and methods

Pgt-infected leaf and stem samples of a local *T. aestivum* bread wheat variety, commonly known as Drubeka, were collected from Norbugang in Samar within the Haa district between late July and September 2025. These tissue samples were then processed using the MARPLE diagnostics genotyping platform (8). In brief, *Pgt*-infected plant samples were disrupted in lysis buffer (200 μ L; 10 mM Tris-HCl, 1 mM EDTA, 0.1% (w/v) SDS) and following centrifugation the supernatant (150 μ L) was mixed with SeraSil-MagTM 400 magnetic beads (30 μ L; Cytiva, Washington, USA) and binding buffer PB (360 μ L; Qiagen, Manchester, UK), before incubation (5 min.; room temperature) to allow the DNA to bind to the beads. After a pellet was formed, the supernatant was removed, and the beads were washed twice with ethanol (500 μ L; 80%). DNA was recovered by adding an elution buffer EB (50 μ L; Qiagen, Manchester, UK), before incubation (5 min.; room temperature) and collection of the supernatant containing DNA. The resulting DNA was used to conduct PCR amplification using the AmpliTaq GoldTM 360 Master Mix (Applied Biosystems, Massachusetts, USA) with four MARPLE diagnostic *Pgt* primer pools that are used to amplify a set of 276 highly polymorphic *Pgt* genes and 5 fungicide target genes. PCR products were eluted using the same magnetic bead protocol as above and sequenced on the MinION Mk1B device using the SQK-PBK114.24 library preparation kit and Flow Cells FLO-MIN114 R10.4.1 (Oxford Nanopore Technologies, Oxford, UK). Basecalled reads were used to perform the bioinformatics analysis using the MARPLE diagnostics workflow (9). To identify mutations shared between the Bhutanese *Pgt*-infected field samples and representative isolates, multiple sequence alignments were performed using Clustal Omega v.1.2.4 (10).

Results

Four *Pgt*-infected leaf or stem samples from individual plants of the local bread wheat variety Drubeka, were collected from a single region in the Haa district of Bhutan between late July and September 2025 (**Fig. 1a**). To examine the genetic diversity among the *Pgt* samples and compare

them to global *Pgt* isolates, targeted amplicon sequencing was performed for a set of 276 highly polymorphic *Pgt* genes using the MinION sequencer, following the MARPLE diagnostics protocol (8). An average of 66.5%±10.8% of the 276 gene set was successfully amplified (Fig. 1b), which is above the established threshold required for assignment of field samples within the subsequent phylogenetic analysis (8). As part of the MARPLE diagnostic pipeline, *Pgt* samples were also examined for mutations in five fungicide target genes. This includes the gene encoding the cytochrome 14- α demethylase (*Cyp51*) enzyme targeted by the azole fungicides, which is essential for ergosterol synthesis in fungi (11), and four subunits of the succinate dehydrogenase complex (*SdhA*, *SdhB*, *SdhC* and *SdhD*), which is targeted by the succinate dehydrogenase inhibitors (SDHIs) (12). Two of the five fungicide target genes (*Cyp51* and *SdhD*) displayed sequence variations when compared to the corresponding *Pgt* reference sequences (CRL 75-36-700-3 (13)) (Fig. 1c). We noted, the same six mutations, three in *Cyp51* and three in *SdhD*, were present in all 4 Bhutanese *Pgt* isolates. Of these mutations, two mutations in *Cyp51* were analogous to mutations described previously in *Zymoseptoria tritici* (*Zt*) (14) (S208T and V490L) and shown to reduce azole binding and in turn lower sensitivity to demethylation inhibitor (DMI) fungicides (14). The remaining *Pgt* mutations in *Cyp51* and *SdhD*, have not yet been described in other studies and, thus, any predicted impact on fungicide sensitivity currently remains unknown (12). However, we also found that all *Cyp51* and *SdhD* mutations were not unique to the *Pgt* Bhutanese field samples, as they were also present in global *Pgt* isolates included in the analysis as representatives of the major *Pgt* race groups (Table 1).

Fig. 1. The MARPLE diagnostics genotyping platform was successfully utilised in Bhutan to evaluate *Pgt*-infected field samples, identifying sequence differences in fungicide target

genes. (a) Wheat leaf sample of a local bread wheat cultivar (Drubeka) infected with both stem rust (*Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *tritici*, *Pgt*) and leaf rust (*Puccinia triticina*, *Pt*). **(b)** MultiQC report following execution of the MARPLE diagnostics workflow on four *Pgt*-infected wheat samples, illustrating successful amplification of the majority of the 276 highly polymorphic genes. **(c)** The four *Pgt* samples analysed within Bhutan all contained potential mutations in two fungicide target genes (*Cyp51* and *SdhD*) when compared to the *Pgt* reference (CRL 75-36-700-3 (13)). This included two mutations in *Cyp51* that are analogous to those previously reported for *Zymoseptoria tritici* (14).

Table 1. The occurrence of mutations identified in *Cy51* and *SdhD* found in the Bhutanese *Pgt* field samples among the 102 *Pgt* representative isolates included in the MARPLE diagnostics pipeline.

Gene	Mutation	Isolates with mutation	Isolate country of origin	Reference organism
<i>Cyp51</i>	S204T	102 (100%)	23 (100%)	<i>Zymoseptoria tritici</i>
<i>Cyp51</i>	V492L	102 (100%)	23 (100%)	<i>Zymoseptoria tritici</i>
		IR-03	Iran	
		IR-04	Iran	
		IR-05	Iran	
		SE-01	Sweden	
		M-01	Mexico	
<i>Cyp51</i>	N260S	ET-04	Ethiopia	<i>Puccinia graminis</i> f. sp. <i>tritici</i>
		01MN84-A-1-2	USA	
		87MDG1054A	Australia	
		84MAR10A	Morocco	
		13GER17-2	Germany	
		69KS170	USA	
		DK-02	Denmark	
<i>SdhD</i>	D19G	09ID073-2	USA	<i>Puccinia graminis</i> f. sp. <i>tritici</i>
		00M063C	USA	
		09ID073-2	USA	
		00M063C	USA	
		83ETH6-1	Ethiopia	
		IS-03	Israel	
		IR-02	Iran	
<i>SdhD</i>	S22N	IR-03	Iran	<i>Puccinia graminis</i> f. sp. <i>tritici</i>
		IR-05	Iran	
		87KEN3018-1	Kenya	
		13GER17-2	Germany	
		87MDG1054A	Australia	
		84MAR10A	Morocco	
		13ETH22-2	Ethiopia	
<i>SdhD</i>	A65S	IT-01	Italy	<i>Puccinia graminis</i> f. sp. <i>tritici</i>
		IT-02	Italy	
		IT-04	Italy	
		IR-02	Iran	

To examine the genetic diversity among the four Bhutanese *Pgt* samples and compare these to the global *Pgt* population, we conducted phylogenetic analysis that included an additional set of 102 global *Pgt* samples previously collected across 23 countries (8). This also included 16 *Pgt* isolates that were previously assigned to nine major *Pgt* race groups, termed Clades I, II, III, IV, VI-A, VI-B, VI-C, VII, IX (15). This analysis indicated that the four Bhutanese *Pgt* samples were genetically highly similar to each other, forming their own subclade within the phylogeny (Fig. 2). In addition, the Bhutanese *Pgt* samples had highest genetic similarity to global *Pgt* isolates that belong to Clade IV, which is known to be prevalent across Europe, East Africa and the Middle East (16). In addition, Clade IV *Pgt* isolates were also recently detected in Nepal and Bhutan in 2024 (3). This indicates that the *Pgt* isolates characterised from Bhutan are similar to *Pgt* isolates known to be present in neighbouring countries in the region and are persisting between seasons.

Fig. 2. *Pgt*-infected field samples from Bhutan group with *Pgt* isolates belonging to Clade IV.

The MARPLE diagnostics pipeline was used to classify *Pgt*-infected field samples from Bhutan into one of 12 genetic groups, using a set of 276 highly polymorphic genes. The phylogeny was constructed using an approximate maximum-likelihood model, with two *Puccinia graminis* f. sp. *avenae* (*Pga*) isolates used as an outgroup.

Conclusion

Here we confirmed the occurrence of *Pgt* infection in 2025 on bread wheat cultivated within Bhutan. In addition, identification of mutations in the *Cyp51* and *SdhD* genes, highlights a need for further lab-based testing on the potential impact of these mutations found across many global *Pgt* isolates on the continued efficacy of azole and SDHIs in tackling *Pgt*. Given the high potential for abundant *Pgt* sexual reproduction to enhance the diversity of *Pgt* in the region, this study highlights the need to enhance wheat rust surveillance efforts in Bhutan for *Pgt* to protect not only Bhutan's wheat production but also neighbouring areas from outbreaks of novel strains.

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